

Patent Application for 3'- Deoxythymidine

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3'Deoxythymidine

The specific synthesis route is not disclosed as many synthesis routes as to 3'deoxyadenosine are formlike in how we would synthesize 3'-Deoxythymidine. And there exist pretty safe methods with high yield and low toxicity such as proposed by T. Fujishima. As the substances Adenosinetriphosphate, Adenosinediphosphate and Adenosinmonophosphate, so can not only the purines (Adenine, Guanine) but also the pyrimidines (Cytosine, Thymine, Uracil).

Therefore 3'deoxythymidine must be phosphatable the same way and has broad applications in the body.

The 2'-Deoxythymidine analoga apperas in several sources as existing (naturally occurring) already but not the 3'Deoxythymidine as suggested in this patent application. (Lewis). It is reasonable to belive that 3'Deoxythymidine has enhanced teratogenic properties or can lead to apoptosis. Wich would make in defeating several micro organisms as well as locally on cancer cells. (As cancer cells need purines as well as healthy human cells in DNA replication, mitosis and cell proliferation on the whole. In the search 3'Deoxythymidine occurs as well but in every occurence is listed with a Lewis structure representing. And even the ball and stick models are showing 3', 2'-Deoxythymidine not 3'-Deoxythymidine, even if it is called such. (National Library Of Medicine, 2025). The overall formula is $C_{10}H_{14}N_2O_4$

I, the applicant, apply for a patent on this very specific analoga 3'-Deoxythymidine wich is given by the overall formula $C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_5$ wich clearly shows that its not the same substance.

Process occurs in cordyceps fungi metabolism and is therefore believed to be applicable to not only purines but also pyrimidines

(go.drugbank, u.d.)

Knowing that the mitochondria use Guanine instead of Adenine, the **3'-Deoxyguanosine** substance is highly likely to be a mitochondria toxin. While also having as broad affects as 3'Deoxyadensine (or Cordycepin) but likely also affecting, muscle contraction, photosynthesis, intracellular cascades and intracellular signal transmission (trough cyclic 3'-Deoxyguanosine (c3'deoxyGMP)). It seems therefore to be of high usability in targeting cancer cells locally, by acting upon the intracellular mechanisms from yet another 'key to lock principle' where it could target pathways not targetable by the closely related 3'Deoxyadenosine. To my suprise: The patent for a process of producing 3'-deoxyguanosine is held by Tetsuro Fujishima. The patent, US4594320, was already issued in April 1983.

By the same natural principle we do obtain another analog of Thymidine: 3'-Deoxythymidine which is not patented but likely the only sensible (since it is the least modified analog of the natural occurring form).

To my knowledge there are only patents of a related substance AZT (zidovudine), for initially held by Burroughs Wellcome Company (Patent #4,724,232)

(cptech, 2000).

3' deoxycytomidine is already held by several US companies, as 3'-Deoxyuracil as well.

Cited

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